

STUDENTS' USES OF GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: PERCEPTIONS, BENEFITS, AND CHALLENGES*

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Abstract

Generative artificial intelligence is a game changer in higher education, offering students and faculty innovative tools for learning and content creation. Capable of generating text, images, and other media in response to user requests, GenAI has become a central topic of discussion due to its potential to enhance personalized learning experiences while raising important questions of ethics and academic integrity. Our study focuses on students enrolled at the Higher Institute of Information and Communication (ISIC) in Rabat. It aims to examine their relationship with GenAI in the academic sphere. The ISIC has shifted its focus toward training student journalists, based on digital literacy. Between the personalization of learning, algorithmic bias, misinformation, and academic dishonesty, understanding journalism students' perceptions of generative AI, as well as its benefits and challenges, is essential for effective integration into their educational framework.

Key words: Journalism students, ISIC, GenAI, AI teaching, Digital literacy.

1. Introduction

The integration of GenAI into journalism education has become a pivotal focus as the media landscape rapidly evolves (Salgado, 2022). This phenomenon is rooted in advancements in technology that have transformed journalistic practices, with AI technologies enabling new forms of reporting, data analysis, and audience engagement. As GenAI gains prominence in newsrooms, journalism educators are increasingly tasked with preparing students to navigate an industry that increasingly relies on these innovations (Gómez-Diago, 2022).

The importance of AI literacy within journalism curricula is underscored by recent disruptions in the media sector, prompting educational institutions to adapt

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their programs to ensure future journalists possess the skills necessary to thrive in an AI-driven environment (Beckett, 2024).

These conversational models hold significant relevance in the higher education, as they enhance students' access to information and streamline the resolution of specific challenges (Gašević et al., 2023). While the integration of AI into Moroccan higher education has sparked discussions, particularly concerning ethical and integrity-related issues, this technology is warmly embraced by the emerging generation of students. Consequently, it is crucial to evaluate its influence on students' learning experiences and cognitive growth. Nevertheless, the existing literature regarding the implementation of AI in the academic sector in Morocco is still sparse. Our research seeks to contribute to this body of knowledge by investigating the impact of AI use on students' creativity and academic achievement in Morocco.

The rise of algorithmic journalism highlights the role GenAI plays in automating tasks traditionally performed by journalists, such as content creation and data reporting (Irfan, 2023). While the incorporation of GenAI into journalism education presents opportunities for enhancing academic skills, it also raises concerns about potential ethical dilemmas, such as algorithmic bias and job displacement within the field of journalism (Salgado, 2022). Critics argue that reliance on GenAI could undermine the core principles of journalism, necessitating a careful balance between leveraging technology and maintaining journalistic integrity (Verma, 2024).

In the 2024-2025 academic year, the Higher Institute of Information and Communication (ISIC) began an LMD (Bachelor, Master & PhD) reform of all levels of training, with the introduction of an English-language journalism track, a first in Morocco.

Prominent initiatives and courses in ISIC focused on AI applications, illustrate the growing emphasis on interdisciplinary approaches to equip students with both technical expertise and ethical understanding. As journalism educators at ISIC develop curricula that incorporate AI, ongoing discussions around transparency, accountability, and the implications of AI-generated content are essential for fostering responsible practices within the field of journalism.

Given that no representation seems to be unanimous, as part of a reflection on the factors anchoring the use of AI among learners' practices, we were particularly interested in students' perceptions of artificial intelligence. Its teaching (Wenger et al., 2025) repeatedly emphasizes procedures, tools, methods, and good practices. However, how do students perceive this teaching in general? What about the use of AI? What are their strategies and tactics for using and circumventing GenAI tools? What is its place in their daily lives for making decisions or responding to informational issues?

Certainly, in a context characterized by a constant evolution of the environment, engaging in the use of AI requires acquiring a digital literacy (Kim & Lee, 2024), having skills in information research, and having the capacity to analyze and evaluate information in order to avoid misinformation (Verma, 2024). Finally,

the structured and rationalized conservation of the information collected and then analyzed remains necessary to gradually and pertinently build up one's information heritage to inform action.

However, while they are particularly predisposed to these issues for which they are also prepared by their training, what uses of AI do information & communication students develop? How are their digital culture and their knowledge of media environments appropriated in this use? We assume that the current state of AI use in academia is moderate.

We hypothesize that apart from the utilitarian nature of AI in the academic circle (final year dissertations, presentations, etc.), it presents an added value for students in their personal lives, in solving their information problems. We also assume that ISIC students mainly use ChatGPT in their daily tasks (production of summaries, writing of press releases and articles, etc.), given that Moroccans are the second largest users in the world (Balaji et al., 2024).

Our article project is organized around three classic temporalities. First, a brief overview of the studies carried out on the representations of GenAI by journalism students. We will also question, in this context, the factors motivating students in their use of AI. In the second part, we will specify the protocol implemented to ensure the collection and analysis of the data for our study. Finally, in the last part, we wish to discuss the results obtained in order to understand how students understand AI and integrate it into their daily activities, both within the framework of their studies and beyond them.

2. GenAI and digital transformation in higher education

A series of studies about the integration of Generative Artificial Intelligence into higher education showed that students report using it for brainstorming, text summarization and article research, while recognizing its usefulness in simplifying complex information (Baidoo-Anu et al., 2024; Ravšelj et al., 2025). AI is often viewed as extension of students' learning strategies, particularly in courses that require writing or conceptual complexity. However, students express concerns about the reliability of the information provided by GenAI and its potential to encourage academic fraud and plagiarism, highlighting the need for clear regulations in universities (Ravšelj et al., 2025).

A study (Qawqzeh, 2024) examines the influence of student interaction with ChatGPT on various cognitive skills and the learning process. 515 participants gather varied perceptions of ChatGPT. The results showed mixed opinions, with some perceiving significant improvements while others noted limited effects. The study emphasizes the importance of responsible use, advocating for guidance rather than direct solutions, and instructor supervision to maximize ChatGPT's potential as a complementary teaching tool. Intriguing correlations were identified between improved critical thinking and its impact on problem-solving and creativity.

A recent study (Baidoo-Anu et al., 2024) carried out among students in Ghana indicates a predominantly favorable perspective on the use of ChatGPT as an educational resource. This perspective is associated with perceived academic

advantages and ease of access. For instance, Ghanaian students indicated that employing ChatGPT has contributed to enhancing their overall academic performance, chiefly due to its assistance in comprehending intricate subjects and ideas. Additionally, ChatGPT allows them to conserve significant time that would otherwise be spent searching for information. Moreover, ChatGPT does not necessitate extensive technical expertise.

In Morocco, few studies have focused on the use of AI in the academic context. A recent research (Baba et al., 2025) investigates the correlation between students' familiarity with GenAI and its application at Cadi Ayyad University in Morocco. A survey involving 370 students was carried out to evaluate their comprehension and utilization of GenAI. The findings suggest that a majority of students are cognizant of GenAI and primarily employ it for language learning; however, there are still significant gaps in their understanding of its limitations and ethical considerations. In terms of GenAI adoption, the study indicates that a substantial portion of participants (87.3%) report using GenAI for language learning (ChatGPT is used by 78.5% of participants). The primary applications of GenAI include vocabulary enhancement (59.2%), writing support (48.2%) and communication (45.6%). Nevertheless, the usage of GenAI for listening comprehension and reading is comparatively lower. Furthermore, respondents recognized that GenAI positively influenced their language skills: 65.1% acknowledged the advantages they provide, and 70.7% expressed satisfaction with these tools, highlighting their perceived effectiveness and utility. Nonetheless, some respondents pointed out the need for improvements in user-friendliness, accessibility, and the incorporation of AI into academic curricula.

Another research (Moussa & Belhiah, 2024) involving 62 undergraduate business law students participating in a general English course at the International University of Rabat investigates the incorporation of GenAI in higher education, with a particular emphasis on the effects of GenAI-assisted writing tools on Moroccan students who are learning English as a foreign language. The results of this survey reveal that GenAI extend beyond mere grammatical corrections, enabling students to enhance their writing through creative expression and improved structural coherence. Moreover, the selection of GenAI significantly impacted the quality of their written assignments, as students exhibited a marked preference for ChatGPT: 93.4% of them use it due to its user-friendly nature and intuitive interface. This implies, as per the study's conclusions, that GenAI has a beneficial effect on language proficiency, vocabulary usage, and overall writing outcomes.

In a research (Moukhliiss et al., 2024) involving Moroccan university students and professors, the authors examine the impact of GenAI on pedagogical approaches and research methodologies, highlighting the potential for tailored learning experiences and enhanced efficiency. They also confront critical ethical dilemmas, such as concerns regarding plagiarism, algorithmic bias, and the necessity for sufficient training for both professors and learners. The authors underscore that, notwithstanding the apparent advantages, limited familiarity and insufficient training

are obstructing the broad implementation of GenAI among the participants, and that the essential role of the teacher cannot be substituted.

Additionally, a research (Ismaili, 2024) examines how to effectively integrate GenAI at Mohammed VI University. It highlights AI's potential to deliver personalized learning experiences, while addressing the ethical and practical challenges associated with its implementation. The results of this survey show that supervised training and institutional support are essential to develop GenAI literacy. The study recommends that institutions should take an exhaustive approach to GenAI integration, including teaching digital literacy and integrating GenAI into academic curricula.

The studies cited above indicate that students' perceptions of GenAI in higher education reveal a complex landscape, marked by both optimism and concern.

3. Methodology

We analyze the comments of 24 Moroccan students in information and communication sciences, interviewed in targeted semi-structured interviews to explore their responses in greater depth, with the aim of understanding their representations regarding the sociocultural issue of AI and assessing its teaching and its effects on their uses. The population considered is composed of first-year bachelor students (L1) in information & communication sciences (Arabic, French, and English sections) and first year of a master's degree in Innovation and Production of Audiovisual and Digital Content (IProCAN) at the Higher Institute of Information and Communication (ISIC) in Rabat. Each of these programs has between 18 and 24 students. The reason for choosing these programs is that the majority of students have received instruction in digital culture during their studies.

First, we verbally informed all of the aforementioned students. We informed them that this was a study conducted among ISIC students who had taken a digital culture course, without revealing our intention to study the subject of this article. The goal was to avoid indirectly influencing them during the interviews. Our sample consisted of students who expressed a desire to be interviewed by contacting us for this purpose. They were enrolled in the Bachelor's degree in Arabic (4 students), the Bachelor's degree in French (5 students), the Bachelor's degree in English (9 students), and the Master's degree in IProCAN (6 students).

Our interviews took the form of a conversation that lasted an average of 25 minutes. They were conducted between May 2025 and June 2025 and were carried out remotely via Microsoft Teams and face-to-face. They were recorded with the consent of the students interviewed.

We used a semi-structured interview guide for the collection of information, so as to avoid distractions and to exclude unnecessary (off-topic) comments from the interviewees. Some questions were used as support to allow interviewees to focus on their uses of GenAI. Our interviewees were given the opportunity to comment on their uses and express themselves freely, recounting their experiences with GenAI. We adopted a flexible approach to ask additional and personalized questions based on the interviewee.

Our interview guide is mainly divided into three parts: first, questions aimed at getting to know the interviewee better, maintaining contact, and establishing trust during the interview; we ask the interviewee to discuss their background and educational curriculum. Second, the interviewee shares their impressions and experiences of the discipline of information & communication sciences in general and the teaching of digital culture in particular. The goal is to ask them how they define GenAI, what motivates them in their academic practices to use these tools, and to understand why they have a particular perception of them. The third theme focuses on the sociocultural aspects of GenAI, while also linking them to their academic lives.

The self-selection sampling is justified by the fact that these are the only classes that have taken a digital culture course, as well as the emerging and sensitive nature of the use of AI (some uses may be informal).

We conducted a thematic analysis, in which the theme served as the unit for segmentation, coding, and analysis. Initially, all interviews were fully transcribed and then imported into NVivo as text files. The coding was carried out using a thematic approach that combined an inductive logic, attentive to the emergence of categories from the respondents' discourse, and a deductive logic, based on conceptual frameworks from the Information and Communication Sciences literature (e.g., technological innovation, contextualization of AI use, perception of AI, and ethical issues related to AI). The units of meaning (sentences, discourse segments, and paragraphs) were grouped into hierarchical thematic nodes (parent and child nodes). The main categories included: representations of AI, actual uses in information production, perceived effects on professional practices, ethical and deontological issues, and the organizational and contextual constraints specific to the Moroccan media landscape.

We transcribed the interviews ourselves. Interviews containing words in Moroccan dialect were directly translated into English during transcription.

In the transcripts of the interviewees' statements, we identified them with the code I followed by the interview number.

4. Results and Analysis

4.1. Varied perceptions of AI-induced cognitive abilities

Our survey participants have diverse perceptions regarding GenAI's influence on critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity: some reported substantial improvements, while others perceived limited or no effects. This variance highlights the complexity of GenAI's impact on academic learning and the need for a fair approach to its implementation in the university. Furthermore, given the diversity of tasks and sectors of activity concerned by GenAI, it is complex to provide a complete overview of students' perceptions, particularly with regard to risk-utility balances. Therefore, we will present a brief overview of these representations relating to GenAI, which continue to evolve.

Notwithstanding these diverse perceptions, the consistent findings of substantial improvements in cognitive areas reinforce GenAI's potential as an educational support tool:

Despite what is said about AI, it is omnipresent in our studies. I use ChatGPT almost every day. It helps me enormously in my studies and allows me to save time and energy. The digital culture course allowed me to use it well (I7, first year undergraduate student, Arabic section, user of ChatGPT, Copy.ai and Grammarly).

ChatGPT is used by all our respondents. This is consistent with the survey (Balaji et al., 2024) cited above, which indicates that Moroccans are the second largest users in the world after India. Our interviewees use GenAI to collect data, generate articles, produce audiovisual content, generate voices, summarize documents, and translate texts.

Prior to the digital literacy course, many respondents held biased perceptions of GenAI, often characterized by confusion regarding its definitions and functions. For instance, several respondents suggested that they associated GenAI solely with robots that process data, underscoring a limited comprehension of the breadth of AI technologies.

Our respondents recognized the effectiveness of GenAI for rapid access to information, as well as its positive influence on interactive and dynamic learning. Overall, ISIC students use AI (primarily ChatGPT) for brainstorming ideas, synthesizing long texts, searching articles for sources, and writing texts (primarily articles or assignments). Use is less common for professional writing, suggesting a student preference for personal expression in this type of work.

The students surveyed perceived GenAI as useful and interesting: most students found GenAI interesting to use. They found it particularly useful for explaining convoluted information and summarizing it. In other words, GenAI provides efficient access to information, overcoming the limitations of manual internet searches. Students find that these tools allow them to quickly gather relevant information and insights for their research.

By entering a question related to an essay topic, the GenAI output can serve as a starting point to develop or deepen students' ideas. We can think of them as writing assistants, capable of improving students' essays. The role of GenAI in synthesizing research results also caught the attention of students: it has the ability to collect, compile, and consolidate information related to a query.

GenAI enhances the learning experience through personalized learning paths. By analyzing a student's search data, AI identifies unique learning styles, such as visuals and interests, and tailors educational content to these preferences. This customized approach allows students to learn at their own pace and focus on their difficulties. Thus, GenAI facilitates the creation of new educational content and optimizes research capabilities. By processing large volumes of academic data, GenAI can synthesize relevant findings and suggest complementary research avenues, allowing researchers and teachers to focus on in-depth analysis and implementation of ideas. Products like SciSpace streamline the research process by combining various features that assist with document querying, keyword extraction,

and summarization. This efficiency not only increases productivity but also contributes to the overall quality of teaching:

Once, the teacher showed us Gemini Education. We did exercises, each at their own level (I18, first year undergraduate student, English section, user of ChatGPT, Gemini and Napkin).

Participants recognize AI's ability to create interactive, engaging, and intellectually stimulating learning environments, as well as to support self-paced learning and facilitate rapid access to information. This perception reflects AI's potential as a catalyst for dynamic learning. GenAI allows a personalized approach and ensures that struggling students receive additional resources, while advanced learners can be challenged with more complex material, effectively filling learning gaps. GenAI also enhances student engagement by creating interactive learning experiences. Gamified learning platforms incorporate game-like elements such as rewards and challenges, making the educational process more enjoyable and competitive. Additionally, GenAI can provide instant feedback and real-time assistance, helping students stay motivated and focused on their learning goals. This interactivity fosters a dynamic environment that encourages active participation and strengthens the learning process.

However, students were less likely to believe that GenAI provides reliable information and supports classical classroom learning:

We're so dependent on AI that we're drowning in misinformation and we lose our critical thinking. We consume everything AI gives us and that's it [...] although we have to admit that it gives us a lot of creative ideas (I16, first year undergraduate student, French section, ChatGPT&Gemini user).

While GenAI serves as a tool that enhances students' creativity and curiosity while enabling them to improve their academic performance, its use presents certain challenges, particularly the risk of accessing to incorrect information, which could adversely affect students' success in developing autonomous critical thinking skills. Additional concerns arise regarding an excessive reliance on AI, which may hinder the comprehensive development of analytical and evaluative skills.

According to the students surveyed, AI should prioritize clues or explanations over providing direct solutions. This preference aims to preserve academic integrity and cultivate a learning environment where understanding takes precedence over simply obtaining answers. Furthermore, many respondents expressed a desire to use AI that provides references to the results obtained. This demonstrates an interest in leveraging it as a resource to facilitate learning and deepen understanding.

In summary, students are likely to develop positive representations due to certain benefits offered by GenAI. Positive attitudes reflect perceived educational utility, which includes improving learning efficiency, perceived educational benefits, and recommendation potential. On the other hand, negative representations

mainly reveal three categories of concerns. First, misuse of GenAI can lead to undesirable behaviors such as plagiarism and cheating. Second, GenAI can negatively impact students' creativity by facilitating quick and easy task completion, which could hinder the generation of original ideas. Finally, excessive reliance on GenAI can lead to technology addiction.

4.2. Ethical and social implications of the use of AI in Moroccan academia

GenAI presents a variety of challenges within higher education, influencing teaching methods, academic integrity, and the overall educational ecosystem. Addressing these challenges necessitates thoughtful consideration and strategic responses to guarantee that the incorporation of AI technologies enhances the learning environment.

Students may misuse GenAI to produce plagiarized content or cheat on their assignments, leading to ethical dilemmas; which creates a broader problem of maintaining academic standards:

We have classmates with us who plagiarize with AI in their class presentations or homework. Sometimes, they blindly humanize the content generated by AI to avoid plagiarism (I14, first year undergraduate student, IproCAN Master, user of ChatGPT, DeepSeek, Gemini and Notebook LM).

One of the most pressing issues surrounding GenAI is its impact on academic integrity. This technology allows students to write dissertations, reports, and other academic papers without meaningfully engaging in the learning process, complicating traditional notions of authorship and originality.

The use of GenAI can hinder the development of essential skills due to the ease with which students can generate content. By allowing AI to generate answers and complete tasks, students risk missing out on opportunities for critical thinking and problem-solving, hindering their intellectual development and learning experiences. This brings us back to the notion of “brain rot” (Yousef et al., 2025) which was chosen as Oxford’s Word of the Year 2024.

The integration of GenAI into academic settings may reduce the quality of teacher-student interactions. As students rely more heavily on AI for answers, the essential communication dynamics of education could be negatively affected, which is crucial for effective learning environments:

Sometimes, I don't ask the teachers the question. I ask ChatGPT instead. The advantage of AI is that it's free and I don't have to pay to access the information. There's always a risk of misinformation. So, I check and compare (I21, first year undergraduate student, IproCAN Master, user of ChatGPT, DeepSeek and Invideo).

GenAI can reduce financial barriers to education. By offering zero- or low-cost tutoring, it makes resources more accessible to students, thereby “democratizing” education. However, ISIC students are more likely to encounter

manipulated content and misinformation, given that all learners use free versions of GenAI. This financial divide raises questions of digital equity, potentially impacting students' academic performance and future prospects.

The reliability of GenAI content is an issue. This observation is not specific to Morocco; several studies (Li et al., 2023) in other countries have also indicated this. ISIC students are trained to critically evaluate information provided by GenAI to ensure its accuracy, as GenAI outputs can often be unreliable or contain bias. This requirement for critical evaluation raises concerns about the level of digital literacy required of students, highlighting the need for greater AI literacy and ethical understanding in higher education.

A major concern of ISIC students is the potential for GenAI to impair their cognitive abilities. Overreliance on AI dialogue systems can foster addiction and discourage critical thinking, leading to uncritical acceptance of generated content. This challenge underscores the importance of educational strategies that encourage students to thoughtfully engage with GenAI while maintaining their analytical skills. In order to reduce the excessive dependence on GenAI, educators in digital literacy emphasize the importance of cultivating critical thinking abilities in their students. Additionally, digital literacy courses can lead to a more cautious and risk-averse attitude toward artificial intelligence. By incorporating GenAI into educational tasks, these teachers motivate students to critically analyze GenAI materials, thereby enhancing skills such as evaluating the credibility of information and scrutinizing audiovisual content. This methodology promotes a well-rounded comprehension of AI's functionalities alongside the indispensable worth of human insight and creativity.

4.3. Contextualization of AI in the Moroccan context

Training datasets form the foundation of artificial intelligence models, but they can also generate biases. If the data used for training lacks diversity, the artificial intelligence risks reproducing these biases. This can lead to cultural insensitivity, as the GenAI may not grasp or respect cultural subtleties. For example, a GenAI trained primarily on Western data may have difficulty understanding Eastern cultural contexts:

In the digital culture course, we saw that AI tools are designed for Westerners. We noticed a strong influence of American culture in the results and recommendations of these tools. In English, queries relevance is almost always there (I16, first year undergraduate student, French section, ChatGPT and Gemini user).

If AI training data comes primarily from a specific culture (such as the USA, where ChatGPT and Gemini were developed), the model will be less effective for other cultures. In other words, GenAI systems may not be exposed to data representative of all cultures, which limits their ability to generalize and perform accurately in diverse cultural contexts. For example, speech recognition models trained on English data may have difficulty understanding accents or dialects of North African origin. Moreover, a GenAI's response is expected to be identical for the same query, regardless of the language used. However, the difference between

querying GenAI in French and English highlights cultural bias: GenAI systems can reproduce or amplify cultural biases.

Students also noticed biases in GenAI, which reflect gender stereotypes:

We noticed in class that when we ask Deepai to create an image of a 'rich person', it presents it with white men of a certain age. Similarly, with the term 'nurse' in English, which is gender-neutral, it only offers images of female nurses (I2, first year undergraduate student, Arabic section, user of ChatGPT and Deepai).

A study published in 2024 by UNESCO and the International Research Center on Artificial Intelligence, on the occasion of International Women's Day, indicated that the large language models developed by Meta and OpenAI, which form the basis of their GenAI, transmit sexist, racist, and homophobic biases (UNESCO & IRCAL, 2024). This study uses different methods, including word association analysis and text generation, to quantify these biases. As an example, it cites the underrepresentation of women in AI development and leadership roles, which creates systems that do not consider the diverse needs and perspectives of all genders.

Beyond gender, artificial intelligence can also consider subjective factors such as ethnicity and age when creating content. The example given by I2 refers to the representation of gender and ethnicity in AI-generated characters; this often reflects societal prejudices and stereotypes rooted in dominant cultures. This inaccurate representation can lead to a limited and biased understanding of the diversity of identities and experiences. Most of our respondents are aware that GenAI systems often reflect the cultural perspectives of their designers, which can lead to a lack of inclusivity and accuracy in the representation of the results generated by these systems.

Concerns regarding ethical dilemmas were amplified during our interviews. ISIC students expressed worries about the cultural biases produced by GenAI, advocating for a "decolonization of computing" that acknowledges and incorporates a variety of cultural viewpoints:

At times, I consult Copilot for guidance, but his suggestions often conflict with my cultural values [...] on one occasion, I sought his advice on a personal issue, and it recommended that I disregard my family and pursue my own path. Ultimately, I chose to ignore his advice (I6, first year undergraduate student, English section, user of Copilot, DeepSeek and Invideo).

The individualistic nature of Western societies (Bentahila, 2023), which prioritizes privacy and autonomy, may lead to a more skeptical perspective on AI. In contrast, the collectivist ethos prevalent in North African nations, such as Morocco, places a higher value on community and social cohesion (ibid.: 101). It appears that adherence to cultural values can cultivate a more favorable view of AI, particularly when it is perceived as beneficial to the communal life of students.

Participants that are from non-Western backgrounds report feeling uneasy with AI systems that fail to acknowledge their cultural values or narratives, prompting them to advocate for a more inclusive approach to GenAI development that respects and integrates a range of cultural perspectives.

Exposure to a singular cultural viewpoint within the artificial intelligence perpetuates the notion that this "cultural hegemony" constitutes the sole valid perspective for AI. In this regard, cultural algorithms (Dourish, 2016) emphasize Western standards (Shahid & Vashistha, 2023). Individuals hailing from non-Western backgrounds may encounter sensations of cultural inferiority or a diminishment of their cultural identity, as their intrinsic values and beliefs frequently remain eclipsed.

This inequality prompts apprehensions regarding the potential detriment to service quality for non-Western students, who might be compelled to exert extra effort to attain outcomes that are on par with those of their Western counterparts. Additionally, it is evident that GenAI impacts the writing styles of certain respondents, resulting in a homogenization that aligns closely with Western standards, thereby threatening to obliterate the nuances of non-Western cultural expression:

The instructor provided examples to highlight the cultural divide. We voiced our apprehensions about the AI outcomes, which seemed to favor "Western cultures," prompting him to modify the course to incorporate cultures like ours in the research findings. This adjustment proved to be highly advantageous for us [...] and assisted in preventing a narrow or uniform perspective (I9, first year undergraduate student, English section, user of ChatGPT, Perplexity and Claude).

I9 articulated concerns regarding the dominance of Western cultural standards in the AI outcomes. The cultural disparities evident in the GenAI results motivated the instructor to incorporate students' cultural backgrounds, thereby enhancing engagement and educational results within the framework of culturally relevant pedagogy. This advancement in AI teaching methodologies situates students in an environment that encourages the inclusion of varied cultural viewpoints in the application of GenAI while fostering the development of culturally inclusive content.

In light of these obstacles, our respondents have called for the incorporation of varied cultural perspectives in AI development. They championed a more sophisticated comprehension of the cultural facets of GenAI, while underscoring the necessity to transcend geographical classifications and foster inclusivity, ensuring that AI caters to a universal audience, mirroring the diversity of human experience rather than reinforcing a singular worldview.

5. Conclusion

The attitudes of the surveyed students regarding GenAI vary from optimism to skepticism. Some students convey excitement about the potential of AI to positively impact learning, while others exhibit a more cautious stance. This

variation in perspectives indicates that continuous dialogue and customized educational approaches will be crucial in addressing the diverse attitudes of students toward AI.

However, it is crucial to note that while students appreciate the potential benefits of GenAI, they also express concern about its impact on critical thinking. The future of journalism education hinges on this careful integration of AI technologies, ensuring that students are prepared not only to use GenAI but also to critically engage with the ethical challenges that accompany their use.

Moroccan students recognize and encounter bias in AI technologies due to misrepresentations of gender, the emphasis on specific cultural viewpoints over others, and insufficient cultural inclusion in the design and outcomes of AI systems. These biases illustrate the wider consequences of cultural hegemony in the evolution of AI technologies. This situation prompts essential inquiries about equity and data representation within AI systems, as the biases ingrained in these technologies may reinforce prevailing stereotypes and cultural insensitivities.

Indeed, one of the original features of our article is to establish the share, which is linked to the use of GenAI in the sociocultural sphere of students from countries in North Africa.

Furthermore, this article can not only serve as a bibliographic reference for future studies, but also open up avenues for reflection on the relationship between AI and the sociocultural context in which it is taught.

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